

DO MEDICAL STUDENTS NEED ENGLISH LANGUAGE COURSES AT HIGHER EDUCATION? (A CASE STUDY IN ONE MEDICAL UNIVERSITY AND 2 COLLEGES)

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Annotation: The work aimed to take needs analysis regarding medical students' attitudes towards the importance of learning English. One state university and two medical colleges in Kashkadarya were investigated by interviewing principals and holding an open seminar with students. Secondary Data Collection methods were used in our research such as Literature Review and Government Databases. Most importantly, an online survey was conducted among 229 students.

Keywords: medical English, pediatrics, President's decree, reforms, language proficiency, certificate, education, teaching, bilingual books

INTRODUCTION

The study took the following steps: We studied a brief overview of the medical faculty of Karshi State University. Following this, we investigated the current state and content of existing English language courses for medical purposes in medical institutions within the Kashkadaryo Region, particularly Karshi State University.

The government is bringing the development of healthcare field and teaching foreign languages into focus. Large-scale reforms are currently being carried out by the state, especially in the regions in the field of training qualified medical personnel and introduction of modern technologies giving positive results. Great attention is paid to the development of the healthcare system and medical education in Kashkadarya region. There are opportunities for further improvement of this system in the future. In particular, technological innovations, training qualified specialists, and expanding high-quality medical services can make a significant contribution to

the social development of Kashkadarya region. Enhancing the quality of existing educational establishments is going well. In addition, today private sectors have a permission to establish new medical university or colleges in Uzbekistan. The main aim behind these reforms and changes is to provide citizens with quality healthcare services.

DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

In Kashkadarya, (southern region of the country) the number of medical educational establishments (both state establishments and private ones) is increasing in recent years. For example, the medical faculty of Karshi state university:

Faculty History. Based on the Decree No. PF-6110 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 12, 2020, the Faculty of Medicine was established at Karshi State University. The main objective of the faculty is to train family physicians. Undergraduate programs: General Medicine, Pediatrics.

The Faculty of Medicine enrolls 781 students in the General Medicine and Pediatrics undergraduate programs. The faculty comprises one department, a simulation lab, two teaching laboratories, and one research laboratory. Additionally, 18 medical institutions located in Karshi city have been designated as "clinical bases" to facilitate student clinical rotations.

Department History. The Department of General Medicine and Pediatrics was established within the Faculty of Medicine at Karshi State University on May 17, 2023, under University Order No. 221X.

Primary Objectives: The department's primary objectives are to provide high-quality education to students and conduct scientific research.

Research Current research focuses on the causes and risk factors associated with maternal and infant mortality, utilizing data from cities and districts within the Kashkadaryo Region.

Collaborations: The department has active collaborations with leading medical institutions to improve its academic and research opportunities. Collaborations include:

- Tashkent Medical Academy
- Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute
- Samarkand Medical University

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

On 3rd July of 2024, The Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation and the Ministry of Preschool and School Education made a joint decree: "On approval of the list of nationally and internationally recognized certificates determining the foreign language proficiency and general education subjects".

According to it, the list of national and international certificates defining the level of knowing foreign languages recognized for admission to post-higher education (master's and doctoral studies) in the academic year 2024-2025 was approved.

The approved list is here. English:

- International English Language Testing System –IELTS (Academic)
- Nationally recognized certificate of knowing English (CEFR).
- Test of English as a Foreign Language – TOEFL Ibt
- Test of English as a Foreign Language (TOEFL iTP)
- Cambridge Assessment English (FCE, CAE, CPE)
- International Test of English Proficiency iTEP Academic.

According to the President's decree, the Ministry of Health, the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education on the reorganization of 47 medical colleges into public health technical schools named after Abu Ali ibn Sina starting from the 2020/2021 academic year the proposal was approved.

Qarshi Abu Ali ibn Sino Public Health College.

Karshi Abu Ali Ibn Sina Public Health Technical College is an institution specializing in the training of highly qualified personnel in the field of health care. The technical school has modern educational programs, experienced teachers and sufficient conditions for practice. There are more than 1200 students studying in different subfields: medical preventive work, treatment work, nursing work, etc.

There are other medical colleges in the region, such as Karshi Ilm-ziyo medical college, Karshi innovational medical college and Shakhrisabz medical college. In addition to these colleges, private universities are also being organized. For instance, medical faculty of Turon private university has started the admission for applicants to study (2024).

According to the research findings in which 229 medical students participated, there is a strong correlation between the English language competency of students and their academic and career goals. It was a questionnaire containing 10 the most necessary questions. The questions targeted to identify their current language levels, what resources they need to learn English independently, what their educational establishments can do to provide better language learning, and their intentions to continue their Master's degree (which requires a language certificate for admission), etc.

As for the EMP resources, creating and providing them with appropriate learning materials is highly in demand. They wanted to have a bilingual medical dictionary with only medicine-related words defined in English-Uzbek. (both traditional paper form and mobile app version of it).

Next importance should be given to preparing graded bilingual books to learn grammar and vocabulary in a progressive and level-by-level manner. It should cover both linguistic and medical content. Grammatical structures should be explained in context instead of focusing only on rules and the form itself. From A 1 to C1 (level), each book needs to be specialized to learn each language level in an ordered way. As

foreign language educators, by creating these materials we should minimize the period as much as possible they spend on learning English, obviously because being obsessed with the language itself should not impact their main major—medical subjects. Most likely, such materials are not available with an English-Uzbek explanation.

CONCLUSION

The research findings suggest an urgent need for a specialized "Medical English" course to meet the diverse language needs of medical students. The course should employ a variety of teaching methods, authentic materials, and specialized resources to provide students with necessary language skills for their future careers. By addressing the diverse needs of students and implementing effective language instruction, medical institutions can empower future doctors to become globally competent professionals.

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